

Climate_CRICES PROJECT

D. 2.1.2 Report on the transborder climate change effects' projections to be analysed

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Summary

Deliverable D2.1.2 summarises the results of Activity 2.1, providing a practical preparation package for the WP2 piloting phase (Activities 2.2–2.4). It consolidates partner contributions from local preparatory activities, identifies key implementation challenges and establishes a joint work plan alongside a corresponding risk management strategy. It also confirms the three transborder working groups aligned with the pilot actions.

In this report, 'projections to be analysed' refers to the agreed scope of what we will work on during the pilots, including priority climate change effects, indicators and datasets, and the questions we intend to answer using the Climate_CRICES dashboard (along with any necessary supporting methods). The pilot phase is organised around three themes: heat and drought; flooding; and biodiversity impacts. The results are intended for use in planning purposes and should therefore be presented as concise, policy-relevant interpretations backed by reproducible dashboard references (views, filters and exports) and compiled into addenda linked to the relevant reference plans in each pilot context. These addenda will support planning up to 2050 and are intended as technical documents for stakeholder validation and policy work.

Bottlenecks are summarised as implementation constraints that have been identified during the activity. These constraints are grouped into eight categories: coordination, capacity, data, dashboard workflow, stakeholder engagement, training, cross-border cooperation and addenda and policy integration. These are linked to monitorable risks in the consolidated risk register. Annex 1 contains the detailed notes on each bottleneck, while Annex 2 contains the full risk table.

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Report on the transborder climate change effects' projections to be analysed

Introduction

Climate_CRICES Work Package 2 (WP2) is testing a data-driven approach to strengthening the capability of regional authorities to develop and use climate change projections in adaptation planning. Within WP2, Activity 2.1 ('pilot action preparatory activities') involved combining eight local training activities with a transborder, peer-to-peer step to harmonise inputs and expectations across regions, as well as forming pilot action teams.

Deliverable D2.1.2 translates the outputs of Activity 2.1 into a preparation package for the piloting phase (Activities 2.2-2.4). It (i) summarises partner inputs from the local activities, (ii) identifies bottlenecks, (iii) provides a joint workplan and a related risk management plan, and (iv) confirms the establishment of three pilot action working groups.

In this report, 'projections to be analysed' means the agreed scope of pilot analyses: priority climate change effects, indicators and datasets, and the main questions to be addressed with the dashboard and supporting methods. The pilots cover (a) heat and drought, (b) flooding, and (c) biodiversity impacts. Addenda interpret projections with a planning horizon up to 2050, as required in the Application Form.

A cross-border pilot for the tri-border Neisse catchment (PL-DE-CZ) is part of the WP2 setup. Partners collaborate with associated partners and relevant authorities to test cross-border usability and realistic uptake pathways.

Input sources and methodology

Inputs

This deliverable is based on:

- Partner inputs from Activity 2.1 and related workshop documentation. Full regional work plans are provided in Annex 3.
- Working documents supporting pilot preparation and internal alignment (bottleneck analysis in Annex 1; risk register in Annex 2; consolidated addendum notes; WP2 coordination notes).
- Methodological baseline from the Application Form and selected WP1 deliverables, used to keep terminology and the data logic consistent (impacts - indicators - datasets - policies - measures).

Methodology

Each partner provided a regional work plan using a standard set of fields aligned with D2.1.2 requirements:

1. Which Pilot Action(s) PP is involved in,
2. What type of addendum or contribution is realistically feasible in PPs context,
3. Key dependencies or constraints that may hinder the Pilot Actions
4. Stakeholders who will consult and validate addenda, plan for cooperation
5. A work schedule that includes peer to peer collaboration between regions.

The synthesis follows four steps:

1. Extract partner inputs into a common frame (pilot actions, addendum type, constraints, stakeholders, schedule).
2. Map statements to the shared data logic to keep terminology consistent without forcing artificial alignment.
3. Cluster bottlenecks into eight categories and link them to risk IDs in the consolidated register. The detailed bottleneck notes are provided in Annex 1 and the full risk table in Annex 2.
4. Apply precedence rules for inconsistencies.

If a statement differs between an older document and a partner's latest input, the latest partner input is used. If partners differ between themselves (e.g. feasibility of formal addendum adoption), differences are reported explicitly as context constraints rather than averaged out, and treated as risks or dependencies in the workplan and risk register.

Implications of dashboard release timing for pilot readiness

The pilot preparation in Activity 2.1 was implemented in parallel with dashboard restructuring. Early trainings relied on a Prototype V1 and later showcased a Prototype of Version 2, published on 12.01.2026. Because full datasets, computed indicators, and linked external data-library functionalities were not yet deployed in the training prototypes, partners used the trainings to validate the planned dashboard structure, define the minimum common indicator scope for pilots, and confirm what content must be integrated in the next release to support testing and addenda preparation.

As a result, the workplan prioritises (i) stabilising the metadata and indicator model, (ii) integrating partner-provided datasets and references, and (iii) adding an interpretation layer (assumptions, limitations, and “how to use” notes) before stakeholder validation cycles start in the pilot phase.

Conclusions of inputs from local activities

Partner inputs from Activity 2.1 are summarised below. Full regional work plans are provided in Annex 3.

LP01 + PP02 (Veneto Region + ARPAV, IT)

- **Prioritised phenomena:** water scarcity and prolonged drought, floods and hydrogeological instability, extreme events, heat waves, and sea level rise (with drought highlighted as particularly important for irrigation and drinking water actors).
- **Reference plan / policy anchor:** Regional Climate Change Adaptation Strategy (SRACC).
- **Addendum concept:** technical support document for SRACC implementation, including a climatological study (historical 1991-2025, projections to 2100) and operational tools for accessing hydro-climatic data, measures and response indicators via the Climate_CRICES dashboard and existing regional platforms.
- **Cross-regional data need identified:** demand from Land Reclamation Consortia for hydro-meteorological data at river-basin scale spanning two regions, which conflicts with the current region-based organisation of monitoring systems and databases.
- **Key constraints:** data updating workflows for the dashboard, and stakeholder engagement across different skill levels in specialised data/platform use.

PP03 (CSI, Piedmont, IT)

- **Pilot focus:** PA1 and PA2, with an addendum targeting integration proposals for the Regional Strategy on Climate Change.
- **Main needs (technical and organisational):** agriculture-relevant heat and drought indicators and clearer interpretation guidance.
- **Constraints:** stakeholder interest exists, but contributions so far have been limited.

PP04 (Forschung Burgenland, AT)

- **Prioritised risks:** Extreme weather-events like heat waves, droughts and water scarcity (mainly in Northern Burgenland) and floods. Loss of biodiversity and further related impacts (e.g. effects caused by neophytes)
- **Reference plan / policy anchor:** Regional Climate Change Adaptation Strategy of Burgenland will be part of the planned Climate Strategy 2040 of Burgenland (currently in preparation)
- **Addendum concept:** Technical support document including Climate_CRICES dashboard (data, measures and indicators) as operational tool either as Annex or contribution for the content of the planned Climate Strategy 2040 of Burgenland and/or as Annex for existing Concepts of the Climate Change Adaptation Regions (CCAR /KLAR)
- **Key constraints:** Missing biodiversity projection datasets and unclear data updating workflows for the dashboard

PP05 (Central Danube Development Agency, HU)

- **Prioritised risks:** drought and water shortage, linked to heat waves and biodiversity impacts, with a sector focus on viticulture and winemaking.
- **Addendum concept:** a package that can be incorporated into the regional Operational Programme during its upcoming review.
- **Key barrier for pilot usability:** uncertainty and multi-scenario projections are confusing for municipal staff, reducing confidence in using the data.
- **Other reported constraints:** competing stakeholder attention (vine disease currently dominates), and dependency on dashboard availability for pilot timing. Limited capacity for in-depth data analysis among decision-makers and farmers,

and sustainability concerns about long-term dashboard operation and funding after project end.

- **Requested functionality / approach:** clearer guidance on scenario use, more visual and narrative messages, and features that help users understand context-specificity (eg “do not copy-paste measures across countries”), plus ideas such as identifying similar municipalities for pattern searching.

P06 (REGEA, Zagreb, HR)

- **Prioritised impacts:** heatwaves and urban heat island effects, flash floods from intense thunderstorms, and biodiversity (explicitly noted as under-addressed in spatial planning).
- **Reference documents / uptake route:** SECAP (2019) of the City of Zagreb (planned revision), plus potential integration into a Climate City Contract currently under development.
- **Addendum concept:** annex to the SECAP (2019) revision and links to the Climate City Contract process
- **Key user expectation:** dashboard must be as user-friendly as possible, with fast access to measures, indicators and comparisons, supported by further trainings.
- **General stakeholder signal from engagement activities:** demand for accessible, practice-oriented data, training and capacity development, and integration pathways into state-level platforms.

Neisse tri-border pilot area (DE-PL-CZ: PP07 + PP08 + PP09)

- **Joint output:** a tri-border addenda package for the Neisse/Nisa/Nysa catchment (three separate documents: Heat and drought, Flooding, Biodiversity loss), prepared jointly by PP07+PP08+PP09 and framed as an evidence-first product to reduce maladaptation driven by governance and data inconsistencies.
- **Shared constraints:** limited harmonised indicators (especially biodiversity), non-comparable datasets, language barriers, and capacity limits in local administrations.
- **Prioritised climate risks (tri-border):** flooding/heavy rainfall, followed by heatwaves, drought and rising temperatures, and biodiversity impacts.
- **Uptake framing:** formal annexing to WFD / Flood Directive instruments is unlikely within the project timeframe. The addendum is treated as a technical reference with defined entry points and realistic uptake routes in each country.

Policy anchors and realistic uptake pathways

- **PP07 (DE, Saxony):** flags low feasibility of changing existing documents (e.g., Saxony Energy and Climate Programme 2021) and lack of clarity on what qualifies as a “successful addendum”. Proposes focusing influence on the policy window for Saxony’s adaptation strategy process instead of assuming formal changes to fixed documents.
- **PP08 (PL, Lower Silesia):** anchors work in DPW and the regional climate neutrality action plan (AP-driven), while treating Oder basin instruments mainly as “alignment and compliance check” due to strict cycles and procedures outside project control;

uptake is therefore expected primarily as a voluntary technical reference for institutions working with these plans rather than a formally annexed document

- **PP09 (CZ, Liberec region):** anchors pilot work in the Liberec regional adaptation action plan and municipal entry points (eg Hrádek nad Nisou), and also screens sub-basin planning documents for the Lusatian Neisse for tri-border relevance.

Dashboard and data usability needs

- Stakeholders request practical cross-territory comparison, reliable exports for planning documents, transparent metadata, a curated data library, and, where feasible, connections to external systems.

Stakeholder feedback also confirms that the most pressing practical data application areas are monitoring effects, risk identification, justification of investments, and action planning and reporting. In terms of dashboard usability, respondents prioritised spatial data layers and ready municipal-scale indicators, complemented by interpretation guidance and export/report-ready outputs.

Fig. 1: Pilot Action Structure

Bottlenecks

In Climate_CRICES context, a bottleneck is an observed constraint in project workflows that delays delivery, reduces output quality or comparability, or limits usability of pilot results and addenda. Bottlenecks are distinct from risks: risks are potential events or conditions assessed by likelihood and impact. Where relevant, bottlenecks are linked to risk IDs in Annex 2.

Bottlenecks were compiled from partner inputs and WP2 coordination and then consolidated to avoid duplication:

1. Collect bottleneck statements from partner inputs and working documents (including regional work plans).
2. Cluster them into categories and define their implications for pilot delivery and validation.
3. Impact framing for each bottleneck: (a) how it affects project implementation and (b) what it implies for pilot feasibility, comparability and timing.
4. Link bottlenecks to the risk register where they translate into monitorable risks.

The bottlenecks can be grouped into 8 categories:

1. Consortium coordination and operational clarity
2. Capacity, workload and continuity
3. Data availability and quality
4. Dashboard development and workflow
5. Stakeholder engagement
6. Training activity
7. Cross-border cooperation (Neisse tri-border)
8. Addenda and policy integration

1. Consortium coordination and operational clarity

Main bottlenecks

- Divergent interpretations of tasks, templates and expected outputs
- Lack of clear operational instructions
- Low responsiveness and delayed feedback
- Insufficient feedback loops from pilots to WP-level outputs

Impact on pilots: Inconsistent inputs increase rework, delay consolidation, and reduce comparability and readiness for pilot validation cycles.

Mitigation

- Confirm every agreement in writing: decisions, roles, and deadlines.
- For each new task, provide operational instructions and at least one example.
- WP leaders and partners should meet regularly to track progress and clear up ambiguities early.
- Assign who gives feedback and by when.
- Use one shared knowledge base as the default reference for the consortium (instructions, glossary, templates, methodological notes).

2. Capacity, workload and continuity

Main bottlenecks

- Overload of key partners and task leaders
- Skill asymmetry across partners (uneven output quality, higher burden on expert partners)
- Staff turnover and knowledge loss (plus “single-person dependency” in key roles)

Impact on pilots: Bottlenecks propagate across WPs, slow down dashboard iterations and reduce the quality and stability of pilot preparation materials.

Mitigation

- Use a structured internal mentoring scheme for advanced tasks: experienced partners mentor others on specific methods and workflows.
- Redistribute dashboard-related and other technical workload more evenly.
- At each partner, every key role needs at least two active people assigned to avoid single points of failure.
- Document procedures and decisions so role changes don't stall the work.
- Keep the shared knowledge repository as the default reference.
- WP leaders and the LP should track staffing and availability explicitly and, when issues show up, adjust scope, timelines, or support early.

3. Data availability and quality

Main bottlenecks

- Missing biodiversity and hydrological datasets (limits indicator coverage)
- Inconsistent formats and insufficient metadata (units, assumptions, methods, coverage)
- Incompatible spatial and temporal scales and georeferencing
- Missing or unclear indicator calculation methods

Impact on pilots: Indicators cannot be computed or remain partial, reducing comparability and weakening the evidence base for pilots and addenda.

Mitigation

- Standardise metadata and dataset formats across all partners.
- For each indicator, provide clear methodological guidance (definitions, sources, processing steps, units, QA checks).

- Agree preferred spatial scales and georeferencing standards (e.g., NUTS) wherever possible.
- Where local data is missing, use European or global datasets if it's justified and documented.
- Set internal deadlines and use simple submission checklists to keep data delivery on time. If data is missing or partial, document it explicitly in both the dashboard and the addenda so users see the limits of the evidence.

4. Dashboard development and workflow

Main bottlenecks

- Dashboard structure misaligned with uneven local data availability
- Repeated metadata restructuring requests (delays, instability)
- Uncertainty on historical vs projected data use for specific indicators
- Manual updates due to lack of APIs and delayed data delivery to technical partners

Impact on pilots: Reduced time for testing and stakeholder validation, inconsistent visualisations, and slower iteration cycles before pilots.

Mitigation

- Consolidate the metadata structure, run one final revision round, then freeze it.
- For each indicator, specify exactly what's required for historical and projected data so partners know what to deliver.
- Apply uniform templates for metadata and datasets across the consortium.
- Enforce timely delivery with clear internal deadlines and short submission checklists.
- Document data update procedures and automate the repeatable parts where possible, so the dashboard stays maintainable after the project ends.

5. Stakeholder engagement

Main bottlenecks

- Low interest in participation (information saturation, competing initiatives)
- Difficulty engaging key actors (underrepresentation of decision-makers)
- Low workshop attendance and stakeholder fatigue

Impact on pilots: Weak validation and weaker legitimacy for addenda and dashboard use cases.

Mitigation

- Outreach needs to be targeted: clear messages, and intermediaries who already work with the key groups.
- Workshop formats should be adapted to stakeholder availability and institutional constraints (eg shorter sessions, hybrid formats, targeted briefings)
- Every event should produce tangible outputs: conclusions, maps, data summaries, and agreed next steps.
- Maintain and update stakeholder mapping to include additional relevant actors beyond existing networks; coordinate timing to avoid stakeholder fatigue and event overload

6. Training activity

Main bottlenecks

- Unclear training aims and learning outcomes
- Training-pilot mismatch (content not aligned with what pilots need next)
- Unclear responsibilities for programme design and materials
- Low interest among target users if training remains abstract

Impact on pilots: Reduced uptake of dashboard outputs and weaker ability to use projections in planning workflows.

Mitigation

Focus training on stabilising one shared concept, making the link to pilots explicit, and spreading responsibilities more evenly across partners.

WP2.1 needs a short, agreed aims statement to close open discussions and document the logic of the work. Each partner should provide concrete examples and materials aligned with their pilot and target groups.

7. Cross-border cooperation (Neisse tri-border pilot area: PP07+PP08+PP09)

Main bottlenecks

- Low motivation for trilateral cooperation unless benefits are immediately visible locally
- Language barriers that slow facilitation and coordination
- Lack of an operational roadmap (roles, workflow, milestones, result-sharing)

Impact on pilots: Risk of fragmented or symbolic cross-border outputs and weaker shared indicator/data inputs.

Mitigation

- Cross-border collaboration only works if trilateral activities deliver clear local benefits. Stakeholders need to see value beyond their own municipality or region.
- Make bilingual support the default: translated materials and simple visual tools keep discussions focused and inclusive.
- Put a concrete operational roadmap in place for cross-border tasks, aligned with pilot needs and existing institutions, and explicit on who does what and when.
- Anchor activities in established cross-border bodies so they continue after the project ends.

8. Addenda and policy integration

Main bottlenecks

- Limited access to formal policy processes and decision-making windows
- Misalignment between political/planning cycles and project timing
- Data gaps lowering addenda credibility
- Lack of coherence across pilots (different indicators and formats reduce synthesis)

Impact on pilots: Addenda risk remaining advisory, with weaker embedding in strategy updates and lower trust from policy-makers.

Mitigation:

- Involve policy-makers early and define concrete entry points for adoption from the start.
- Track political and planning cycles in each region, and prepare addenda in a modular, future-proof format that stays usable after the project ends.
- Document methodological choices and data limitations transparently to protect credibility, especially where indicators are partial or uneven across regions.
- Use a harmonised template across partners, with room for justified regional specificity.
- Treat dashboard outputs as the primary evidence base, so recommendations are defensible and practically usable.

Definition of “projections to be analysed” in WP2

In WP2, “projections to be analysed” does not mean generating new climate model simulations. It means agreeing and operationalising a shared analytical scope for the pilot phase: which climate change effects will be addressed, which indicators and datasets will be used (and at what scales), how scenarios and uncertainty will be communicated, and how results will be translated into addenda that can support existing plans.

Common minimum scope

Across all pilot actions, the common minimum analytical scope includes:

- Study area and spatial levels (region, municipality, catchment where relevant).
- Time horizon aligned with planning needs, with projections interpreted primarily up to 2050 as required in the Application Form.
- Baseline and observed trends to anchor interpretation.
- Scenario comparison and uncertainty explanation (requested by stakeholders as a usability requirement).
- A core indicator set mapped to the shared data logic (impacts - indicators - datasets) with documented regional extensions where justified.

Thematic scope by pilot action

The pilot analyses are clustered into three thematic areas that define the required projections and indicators:

- **PA1 - Heat and drought:** heat exposure and heat stress indicators, drought and water scarcity dynamics, sector-relevant impacts where prioritised.
- **PA2 - Flooding:** indicators addressing flooding (including pluvial or flash flood relevance where needed) and related planning implications.
- **PA3 - Biodiversity impacts:** indicators on biodiversity pressures and impacts, with explicit handling of data gaps and substitute indicators where defensible.

Output of the analysis

A projection analysis is considered complete when it is translated into

1. a short interpretation usable in planning,
2. clear links between indicator changes and planning priorities,
3. reproducible dashboard references (views, filters, exports).

Limits and constraints that shape what can be analysed

- Some data gaps (especially biodiversity and local-scale hydrology) cannot be closed within the project and must be reported explicitly.
- Stakeholders expect not only data availability but also interpretation support (definitions, limitations, “how to use”)
- Dashboard technical constraints may limit some requested functions. In such cases, the pilot should propose a practical alternative (export, documented link, external workflow).

Joint workplan for the pilot phase

This joint workplan translates the regional work plans and Activity 2.1 outputs into a minimum shared workflow for Activities 2.2-2.4. It is designed to keep pilots feasible and comparable despite different data maturity, governance settings and uptake routes.

Workplan principles:

- Shared workflow with flexible uptake: common analytical logic and addendum structure, while uptake format may differ (annex, technical reference, documented use).
- Comparability core: align on a core indicator set and metadata rules where feasible.
- Usability: outputs must be usable in planning workflows (clear interpretation, exports, traceable sources).
- Prioritise indicator and dataset choices that support monitoring of impacts and measures (effects tracking), as this was the strongest reported data gap and a key requirement for practical uptake.

Shared workstreams and steps

A) Data and metadata consolidation

- Confirm the minimum dashboard contents for pilot action (PA1-PA3) and decide preferred spatial/temporal scales.
- Prepare the list of datasets needed and provide them with mandatory metadata.
- Where key datasets are missing (especially biodiversity), define fallback indicators and document limits explicitly.

B) Dashboard integration and iteration loops

- Agree a “pilot-critical” feature set and stabilise the dashboard structure to avoid rework during the pilots.
- Implement staged updates: initial pilot-ready version for testing + subsequent incremental improvements based on stakeholder feedback.
- Maintain a clear link between indicator calculations and dashboard representations (methods, scenario handling, timestamps).
- CSI draft timetable of future dashboard releases:
 - March 2026: new navigation and UX

- Further updates are planned, including completing and translating metadata, adding embedding and download features, and (subject to agreement) uploading Copernicus and other basic datasets.

C) Local and transborder working groups

- Each partner organises working groups with authorities responsible for adaptation planning to confirm priorities, validate interpretations, and test dashboard usability.
- A joint tri-border working group supports the Neisse pilot area (PL-DE-CZ).

D) Addenda drafting, validation and uptake planning

- Draft addenda as technical, data-driven supporting documents linked to the reference plan.
- Validate addenda with stakeholders and define a realistic uptake route (administrative, political, financial).
- Ensure addenda include dashboard references so results can be reproduced.

E) Peer-to-peer alignment across regions

- Partner coaching sessions per pilot action to compare inputs, align indicator approaches and agree common messages and limitations.
- Partner meeting to analyse addenda and identify common elements for transnational added value.

Key dates and dependencies are summarised in the Table 1 below.

Table 1. Key dates and dependencies

Date / month	Milestone	Owner/ dependency
27 Feb 2026	Final metadata collection from partners (for pilot use)	All partners
28 Feb 2026	D2.1.1 and D2.1.2 submission	PP08 with partners
End March 2026	Dashboard update	CSI, partners feedback
End March 2026	Deadline for organisation of the Pilot Action kick-off events. Start of preliminary addenda drafting	WG leads, partners
End April 2026	Upload of complete and translated metadata	CSI, all partners
Mid April 2026	Validation of preliminary addenda and first uptake planning	Partners with stakeholders

16-17 Apr 2026	Partners meeting in Wroclaw - analyse addenda and align next steps	All partners
End May 2026	Dashboard embedding and download features	CSI
31 May 2026	PA reports (D2.2.1, D2.3.1, D2.4.1)	WG leads

Pilot-action specific activities:

- PA1 (Heat and drought): partner coaching hosted by LP01 with follow-up peer-to-peer alignment steps among involved partners.
- PA2 (Flooding): partner coaching hosted by PP06.
- PA3 (Biodiversity): partner coaching hosted by PP04 with explicit attention to data gaps and interpretation constraints typical for biodiversity indicators.

Context-specific activities: tri-border region

The tri-border pilot runs with additional coordination needs (language, governance, dataset comparability). PP07, PP08 and PP09 established a regular coordination rhythm and a milestone plan extending through 2026 (division of responsibilities, stakeholder consultation, draft addendum delivery, and a cross-border dissemination event aligned with World River Day timing).

Until end Feb 2026	Decide on who does what (see table above)
Until End April 2026	Finalize the analysis, conduct mini-literature survey and write some of the intro
May/June 2026	Consultation meeting with stakeholders on first results and findings
Until End May/June	Finalize assessments, collate findings and provide first set of coherent draft
Until End Aug. 2026	Provide addenda to respective APs for their vetting
Last week of Sept.	Triborder Event for World River Day - Dissemination event
Until End Oct. 2026	Provide final addenda
Until End Dec. 2026	Obtain signed addenda from APs

Addenda

In Climate_CRICES, an addendum is a scientific and technical supporting document linked to a specific reference plan or strategy. It translates dashboard-based projections,

indicators and analyses into a policy-relevant format that can be validated with stakeholders and used to support plan implementation or updates.

The Application Form frames addenda as containing: projections focusing on a defined climate change effect, indicator-based analysis with comparison up to around 2050, additional locally relevant information, stakeholder validation, and a first plan for uptake (administrative, political, financial).

Addendum roles and uptake types

Partners converge on the addendum as a technical, data-driven overlay to existing plans (not a replacement of the plan and not a catalogue of measures). Differences concern mainly the formality of uptake and how “normative” the addendum is expected to be. Formal uptake depends also on external decision cycles; addenda may remain “working documents” before any formal attachment becomes possible.

Two uptake types are treated as legitimate within the project logic:

1. Implementation-ready policy addendum (administrative uptake): partner has a clear mandate and an established approval route

Uptake form: formal attachment to an official strategy/plan (resolution, annex, procedural attachment).

2. Evidence-first technical addendum (scientific uptake): partner does not control formal adoption pathways (eg research institution, advisory role, cross-border setting).

Uptake form: referenced evidence in planning documents, partial adoption by multiple bodies, technical appendix use, or documented integration into workflows and dashboard use cases.

The Application Form defines intended uptake anchors for each pilot context (SRACC, SECAP, CCAMR, OP and the Neisse river basin planning context), but partner inputs and WP2 coordination notes confirm that uptake feasibility differs strongly by governance setting and legal weight of the reference document.

In particular, the Neisse tri-border pilot area (PP07+PP08+PP09) is expected to rely more on the evidence-first uptake model, because water-law-rooted basin instruments follow strict cycles and formal procedures outside the direct control of project partners and associated partners.

The tri-border addenda are framed as a jointly prepared package (three separate documents: Heat and drought, Flooding, Biodiversity loss) supporting cross-border decision-making and avoiding maladaptation caused by governance, methodological and data inconsistencies. Due to cross-border complexity and differentiated mandates, a realistic pathway may involve one joint narrative core plus complementary “entry-point” documents for municipality, region and cross-border platforms, rather than assuming one formally annexed document across all three countries.

What should and should not be included (common partner view)

Should be included (minimum core):

- Projections focusing on a defined climate change effect
- Indicator-based analysis and comparison of information considering projections up to 2050
- Additional locally relevant information and data
- Validation with stakeholders
- A first plan for uptake (administrative, political, financial) in the frame of the reference plan

Should not be included (to keep the addendum usable):

- long generic climate change background duplicated from other sources
- full catalogues of measures (these belong in the plan itself)
- content contradicting higher-level strategies or legal acts
- excessive technical detail that blocks usability for administrations.

Common minimum addendum structure

A common minimum structure is used to keep outputs comparable while allowing country-specific uptake formats:

1. Purpose and context (reference plan, link to pilot action)
2. Data and methods (study area, time horizon, sources, indicators, main analytical steps, limitations)
3. Results and key findings (baseline and trends, projections and scenarios, spatial patterns and vulnerable areas)
4. Implications for the plan (support for existing objectives, identified gaps, priorities for updates)
5. Dashboard use (reproducibility, recommended use cases, update responsibilities where relevant)

6. Appendices (detailed formulas, extra maps, metadata).

Risk management plan

In Climate_CRICES WP2 context, risk is a potential event or condition that may hinder the delivery of pilot outputs (dashboard-supported analyses and addenda) or reduce their quality, comparability, validation, or uptake. The risk management plan complements the bottleneck analysis: bottlenecks describe observed constraints in workflows, while risks translate those constraints into monitorable threats with mitigation actions and ownership.

Risk management is part of the project governance approach and is expected to be periodically updated and monitored by the partnership structures (Technical Committee and Steering Committee).

Methodology

Risks were identified based on partner inputs and the bottleneck analysis. They were then classified as:

- Project-level risks (affecting the whole consortium and core outputs), and
- Partner-level risks (context-specific, reported by one or more partners).

Risk significance is assessed using:

- Likelihood and Impact on a 3-point scale (Low, Medium, High), and
- a combined risk level (1-9) supported by a likelihood-impact matrix and a descriptive scale from Very Low to Critical, used consistently across the partnership

Fig 2. Graphical representation of risk levels

For partner-level risks, partners assign likelihood and impact for their context. The consolidated register reflects the highest reported likelihood (and the corresponding impact) when aggregating partner inputs, to avoid underestimating constraints in transnational dependencies. High and critical risks are escalated for decision where mitigation requires cross-WP coordination or governance decisions (e.g. changes in scope, major re-prioritisation). Where a risk is driven by an observed bottleneck (e.g. missing metadata, delayed feedback, cross-border operational gaps), the mitigation measures are aligned to address the root workflow issue and not only the symptom.

Table 2. Risk levels

Field	Risk level	Description	Recommended action
1	Very Low	Risk is negligible or easily acceptable.	No action required. Continue regular monitoring.
2	Low	Minor risk, unlikely to significantly affect objectives.	Preventive actions optional.
3	Moderate (Low-Medium)	Low impact but worth attention.	Consider preventive measures to reduce risk further.
4	Medium-Low	Potential impact noticeable under certain conditions.	Monitor closely and plan mitigation if conditions change.
5	Medium	Risk could affect objectives if unmanaged.	Prepare and implement a risk mitigation plan.
6	Elevated (Medium-High)	Likely to require active management.	Take mitigation actions within planned timeframe.
7	High	Significant risk with potential to cause major disruption.	Implement mitigation measures immediately. Assign responsibility.
8	Very High	Serious risk with high probability or severe impact.	Immediate response required. Escalate to decision-makers.
9	Critical	Critical risk threatening core objectives or project success.	Immediate and comprehensive action plan required. Consider avoidance or transfer strategies.

Consolidated risk register summary

The full risk register is provided in Annex 2. The main risk clusters relevant for the pilot phase are:

1. Data availability and indicator readiness

Key risks include lack of essential data (especially biodiversity), missing datasets for core indicators, incompatible spatial or temporal scales, and missing indicator calculation rules, all of which weaken the evidence base for pilots and addenda.

2. Dashboard delivery and data workflow

Key risks include delays in dashboard deployment and limited capacity to integrate dynamic or late data deliveries, reducing time for testing and stakeholder validation and potentially preventing dashboard referencing in pilot outputs

3. Stakeholder engagement and validation

Key risks include low engagement of local authorities, information saturation, stakeholder fatigue, and an insufficient number of engaged stakeholders to validate addenda, which threatens legitimacy and uptake.

4. Cross-border cooperation risks (Neisse tri-border)

Key risks include low motivation for PL-DE-CZ cooperation, language barriers, missing operational roadmap, and limited dashboard support for transborder comparability, which can lead to symbolic rather than functional cross-border outputs.

5. Uptake and institutional embedding (Addenda)

Key risks include limited institutional ability to create or adopt addenda, political cycle misalignment with the project timeline, addenda being perceived as too generic, reduced credibility due to data gaps, and lack of coherence across pilots (different indicator sets and formats).

6. Training and capacity-building

Key risks include unclear training objectives and responsibilities and training-pilot mismatch, which reduces training effectiveness and delays downstream pilot work.

7. Consortium operations and pilot timing

Key risks include overload of key partners, unclear outputs and divergent interpretations, delayed feedback, skill asymmetry, staff turnover and single-person dependency, and unclear pilot timing that disrupts planning and delivery.

Risk monitoring and update process

- Regular check-ins and WP coordination, with escalation of high or critical risks when mitigation requires decisions beyond WP2.
- Periodic updates of the risk register to reflect new dependencies (e.g. dashboard release timing, dataset availability, stakeholder validation constraints).
- The risk register is treated as a living management tool for the pilot phase. It is updated when (a) new dependencies emerge (e.g. dashboard releases, dataset delivery

constraints), (b) likelihood or impact changes based on implementation experience, or (c) mitigation measures require reassignment.

Establishment of 3 pilot groups

In line with the Application Form, WP2 establishes three transborder working groups aligned with the three pilot actions. These groups provide the operational backbone for harmonising inputs, agreeing indicator and dataset priorities, coordinating stakeholder validation, and ensuring comparability of addenda across regions.

PA1 Working Group - Heat and drought

- Working group leader: PP09 (UJEP)
- Partners involved:
 - LP01 + PP02 (Veneto)
 - PP03 (Piedmont)
 - PP04 (Burgenland)
 - PP05 (Central Danube)
 - PP06 (Zagreb)
 - PP07 + PP08 + PP09 (joint Neisse area)

PA2 Working Group - Flooding

- Working group leader: PP08 (UPWr)
- Partners involved:
 - PP03 (Piedmont)
 - PP04 (Burgenland)
 - PP05 (Central Danube)
 - PP06 (Zagreb)
 - PP07 + PP08 + PP09 (joint Neisse area)

PA3 Working Group - Biodiversity loss

- Working group leader: PP04 (Forschung Burgenland)
- Partners involved:
 - PP04 (Burgenland)
 - PP05 (Central Danube)
 - PP06 (Zagreb)
 - PP07 + PP08 + PP09 (joint Neisse area)

Partners designate working group members based on their regional work plans and pilot responsibilities (including technical, policy and stakeholder engagement roles). The working groups interact with local working groups organised in each pilot area, which provide the stakeholder validation function for addenda and dashboard usability.

Conclusions

Deliverable D2.1.2 consolidates the outputs of Activity 2.1 into a shared preparation package for the pilot phase. It summarises inputs from local workshops, identifies bottlenecks, defines a joint workplan and a related risk management plan, and confirms the establishment of three pilot action working groups.

The partner inputs confirm a strong convergence around three priority thematic areas for pilot analyses: heat and drought, flooding, and biodiversity impacts, while also demonstrating that feasibility and uptake routes differ significantly across governance settings. This is especially relevant for the Neisse tri-border pilot area (PP07+PP08+PP09), where cross-border governance differences, data comparability constraints, and limited control over formal adoption pathways require an evidence-first, realistic approach to addenda uptake.

The bottleneck analysis shows that implementation constraints are largely systemic and interconnected: consortium coordination and capacity constraints affect data delivery, dashboard iteration cycles, training effectiveness, stakeholder validation, and ultimately the credibility and uptake potential of addenda. The project response therefore relies on a minimum shared workflow (indicator and metadata consolidation, stabilised dashboard update logic, structured stakeholder validation, and a common addendum template) combined with explicit documentation of limits instead of forced uniformity.

Immediate implications for the pilot phase

- The pilots require a prioritised minimum indicator set and consistent metadata rules before stakeholder validation can be meaningful.
- Addenda must remain concise, reproducible (dashboard links/exports), and explicitly scoped to planning needs up to around 2050 as required in the pilot roadmaps.
- Risk management must be actively maintained as a living register, because dashboard delivery timing and dataset readiness are high-impact dependencies for all pilots.

Annex 1: Detailed bottleneck notes

Annex 2: Full risk table

Annex 3: Regional Work Plans

Climate_CRICES

Climate_CRICES PROJECT

D. 2.1.2 Report on the transborder climate change effects' projections to be analysed

ANNEX 1: Bottleneck Analysis

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Bottleneck Analysis

Introduction

Climate_CRICES is implemented by a multi-country, multidisciplinary consortium working on data-driven climate adaptation planning. This document provides a structured overview of bottlenecks that may hinder effective project implementation. Here, a bottleneck means a recurring weakness or constraint in project workflows that slows progress, reduces output quality or comparability, or limits the usability of results in pilots and policy work.

- Scope and limitations

The document focuses on internal bottlenecks within Climate_CRICES. It does not cover external factors such as changes in EU regulations or national politics. The assessment is qualitative and reflects the current state of information; it should be updated as new risks appear.

Several bottlenecks are cross-cutting and have a disproportionate effect on project progress. Delays in WP1 affect WP2 and WP3 due to strong dependencies between work packages. These systemic issues require coordinated mitigation across several partners and WPs, rather than isolated measures at task level.

The document is meant as a practical tool to adjust current workflows and to plan mitigation measures for the Pilot Action.

1. Consortium coordination and operational clarity

Effective communication in a multi-country, multi-disciplinary consortium is a basic operational requirement, not an added value. This section describes how communication gaps, unclear instructions and low responsiveness affect the consistency and timing of project outputs.

1.1. Divergent interpretations of tasks, templates and expected outputs.

A recurring issue is inconsistent understanding of tasks, templates and expected outputs. Verbal agreements from meetings are not always followed by written summaries, which leads to different interpretations of scope, format and level of detail.

Partners submit materials with uneven quality and structure. As a result, task leaders need extra clarification rounds, deliverables become inconsistent, workload increases and comparability across regions is reduced.

Impact on pilots: Inconsistent inputs slow down pilot preparation, reduce comparability, and increase rework.

Linked Pilot Risks: 4.4, 5.3, 5.5, 7.2

Mitigation:

- prepare written summaries after each meeting outlining decisions, task division, responsibilities and deadlines
- embed clear instructions in all templates and document packages
- use a shared glossary and consistent terminology across WPs

1.2. Lack of clear operational instructions

Several tasks, especially at the start of the project, lacked sufficiently detailed operational guidance. This created uncertainty about the required depth of analysis, links to indicators or pilot needs, and about expected formats for data, metadata and stakeholder inputs.

Partners' contributions were inconsistent, the metadata structure had to be redesigned, and some partners, in particular PP03, faced substantial rework.

Impact on pilots: Inconsistent inputs slow down pilot preparation, reduce comparability, and increase rework.

Linked Pilot Risks: 2.4, 7.2

Mitigation:

- implement step-by-step operational guidance for complex tasks,
- provide examples of correct outputs,
- ensure that every task description is tied to the overall methodology and dashboard structure.

1.3. Low responsiveness from partners (low feedback / delayed feedback)

Limited or delayed feedback from some partners, often due to workload or missing clear deadlines, has been one of the main drivers of project-wide delays.

Collaboration becomes inefficient, dashboard development slows down and the exchange of expertise across the consortium is reduced.

Impact on pilots: Slows collaboration and dashboard development, reducing the iteration cycles needed before pilot validation.

Linked Pilot Risks: 2.1, 2.3, 7.3

Mitigation:

- set explicit feedback deadlines for each task,
- assign responsible persons for review and contributions,
- conduct regular control teleconferences at WP and task level,
- integrate automated reminders and shared calendars.

2. Capacity, workload, and continuity

The Climate_CRICES consortium brings together partners with different expertise, regional contexts and institutional profiles. This section examines how workload distribution, skills gaps and staff turnover affect the consortium's ability to deliver key tasks on time and at a consistent quality.

2.1. Diverse competencies and experience within the partnership (skills gap)

The consortium includes partners with strong climate analysis and data management skills alongside others with more limited capacity in modelling, data processing or indicator interpretation. This asymmetry, while intentional, leads to uneven progress and variable output quality.

Less experienced partners work more slowly, while more advanced partners spend extra time reviewing, correcting or supplementing materials. Harmonised outputs across regions are harder to achieve, and some partners effectively become reviewers or troubleshooters instead of focusing on their core tasks.

Impact on pilots: Uneven pilot quality and slower consolidation of shared methods and outputs.

Linked Pilot Risks: 7.4

Mitigation:

3. introduce an internal mentoring scheme, with experienced partners formally guiding less experienced ones on key tasks
4. allocate specific time for verification and revision rounds, rather than treating them as ad hoc work
5. use shared templates and concrete examples for all partners to limit divergence in structure and content

2.2. Overload of key partners

Project coordination and technical work are concentrated in a small group of partners, which creates a structural risk: any delay or overload in these institutions cascades across work packages. CSI Piemonte in particular acts as the project's digital backbone, so its delays directly affect dashboard functionalities, training content, testing and addenda development.

This results in bottlenecks in dashboard-related WPs, limited capacity for partner support and a strong dependency on a few experts. When these experts are overloaded, progress slows across several tasks simultaneously and some activities stall until they become available.

Impact on pilots: Delays cascade across WPs due to dependencies, reducing time for testing and validation.

Linked Pilot Risks: 2.1, 7.1, 7.4

Mitigation:

- delegate supporting tasks such as user training or basic data preparation to other partners after targeted training from CSI
- bring in additional staff from universities or research units to share the technical workload
- monitor the workload of key individuals and, where necessary, adjust project personnel budgets to reinforce critical roles

2.3. Staff turnover and loss of institutional knowledge.

In a 2.5-year project, personnel changes are unavoidable: contracts end, staff move to other positions and local elections can shift management and priorities. Even if more than one person is officially assigned, practical knowledge about methods, workflows and decisions often concentrates in a small number of individuals.

When these people leave or change roles, methodological know-how and contextual knowledge are at risk of being lost. New staff need time to reconstruct previous decisions and understand data structures, which causes delays, uneven work quality and repeated discussions on issues that were already settled earlier in the project.

Impact on pilots: Slower delivery, inconsistent methods, and increased risk of errors in pilot-relevant datasets/metadata.

Linked Pilot Risks: 7.5

Mitigation:

- document all key decisions, codes, methods, templates and procedures systematically
- establish simple handover procedures for key roles, including short written notes on status, decisions and open issues
- maintain a central knowledge repository, accessible to all partners, as the primary reference point for documentation

2.4. Limited staff availability and single-person dependency

In some partner institutions, only one person is effectively handling day-to-day project work, while others are mostly in advisory roles or blocked by teaching and other duties. If this key person becomes unavailable for a longer period (illness, overload, institutional duties), the partner has very limited capacity to keep up with project management, content development and meeting participation.

Coordination, reporting and content preparation concentrate on one person and quickly create a bottleneck. External support is hard to use efficiently if tasks are not clearly defined or documented. Delays accumulate, task leaders cannot react properly to unexpected absences, and overall project resilience to personal crises remains low.

Impact on pilots: High vulnerability to absence/overload, slow reaction, low resilience.

Linked Pilot Risks: 7.5

Mitigation

- ensure each partner assigns at least two people who understand the core project tasks and can substitute for each other
- document key workflows and decisions so that temporary handover is possible without major disruption
- escalate availability problems early to WP leaders and the LP so that scopes, timelines or supporting roles can be adjusted
- activate cross-partner support after clarifying concrete tasks and expectations, so that external help is targeted and efficient

3. Data availability and quality

Dataset availability, completeness and reliability differ markedly between regions. This section focuses on how uneven data coverage, complex formats and incompatible scales constrain indicator development and cross-regional analyses.

3.1. Lack of available data, especially for biodiversity projections.

Some thematic areas have particularly weak data coverage, notably biodiversity indicators, hydrological datasets for flood-related indicators and long-term climate projections at sufficient spatial resolution. In some regions, authoritative biodiversity datasets are missing or lack temporal depth, while hydrological modelling requires specialised expertise that partners do not have in-house.

As a result, certain indicators cannot be computed or are only partially available, and dashboard visualisations provide limited value for some pilots. Expert partners face additional workload trying to compensate for gaps, and policy recommendations based on incomplete datasets are less robust and harder to justify.

Impact on pilots: Indicators cannot be computed or only partially available; evidence base for pilots and addenda weakens.

Linked Pilot Risks: 1.1, 1.2, 5.4

Mitigation:

1. use European or global datasets (e.g. Copernicus, EEA) as interim sources where local data are missing

2. allow alternative indicators where relevant and methodologically sound.

3.2. Complexity of data preparation (different formats, lack of metadata).

Partners have submitted datasets in multiple formats (CSV, XLSX, shapefiles, map exports), often with insufficient metadata. Information on spatial coverage, temporal range, calculation methodology, units and underlying assumptions is frequently incomplete or missing.

Data are difficult to interpret and integrate into the dashboard. This causes delays in data ingestion, increases the risk of misinterpretation or incorrect indicator calculation and shifts extra cleaning and harmonisation work to technical partners.

Impact on pilots: Delays ingestion, increases risk of misinterpretation and wrong calculations, pushes burden onto technical partners.

Linked Pilot Risks: 5.4

Mitigation:

- mandatory metadata templates,
- require partners to document methodology, units and assumptions in a standardised way
- standardise accepted formats for dashboard integration and provide simple conversion guidance

3.3. Incompatible Spatial and Temporal Scales.

Datasets differ in spatial resolution (from municipal to regional or national), temporal resolution (monthly, yearly, event-based), georeferencing systems and the administrative boundaries or NUTS classifications they use. These inconsistencies are often not documented explicitly.

It becomes difficult to align data with policy documents and indicators or to perform robust cross-border comparisons. Comparability between pilot regions is limited, integration into unified visualisations is complicated and the risk of misleading regional contrasts increases.

Impact on pilots: Hard to align with indicators/policies; cross-border and cross-region comparisons become unreliable; risk of misleading contrasts.

Linked Pilot Risks: 1.2, 1.3, 4.2

Mitigation:

- define preferred scales for each indicator during the final data consolidation,
- provide transformation guidelines (e.g. aggregation, resampling),
- require partners to validate the spatial and temporal relevance of datasets.

4. Dashboard Development & Technical Workflow

The Climate_CRICES dashboard is a core project output and the main interface for visualising climate impacts, indicators, datasets and adaptation policies. This section focuses on technical and organisational bottlenecks that slow down dashboard development and reduce comparability and long-term usability.

4.1. Dashboard not adapted to local data availability.

Data availability differs significantly between regions. Some partners work with well-structured datasets and robust indicators, while others face gaps in historical data, incomplete records or non-standard formats. This complicates the design of a common dashboard structure.

Some indicators cannot be calculated for all areas, visualisations differ in completeness and cross-regional comparisons are weakened. Integration of datasets into the dashboard is delayed and the analytical value remains uneven across the consortium.

complicate one common dashboard structure.

Impact on pilots: Missing indicators reduce comparability; uneven analytical value; delays integration/testing

Linked Pilot Risks: 1.2, 1.3, 2.2, 4.2

Mitigation:

- apply a "minimum common denominator" approach for cross regional comparisons
- clearly label missing data and methodological gaps in the dashboard and related documentation
- allow region specific extensions where justified, while keeping the core structure comparable

4.2. Repeated need to remodel the metadata structure by PP03.

As partners refined their understanding of indicators, impacts and datasets, CSI Piemonte received repeated requests to modify the metadata structure. These revisions reflected evolving requirements and uneven understanding of the common methodology but were time consuming.

CSI's workload increased, dashboard implementation was delayed and the risk of misalignment between metadata and regional datasets grew. Frequent changes also made it harder for partners to stabilise their internal workflows.

Impact on pilots: Delays dashboard readiness and increases risk of misalignment between metadata and datasets.

Linked Pilot Risks: 2.1, 2.4

Mitigation:

- freeze the metadata structure after a final consolidation round,
- provide detailed metadata instructions and fixed templates for all partners
- introduce a validation step to check completeness and consistency before data submission

4.3. Uncertainty regarding the use of historical data versus projections.

Uncertainty remains about which data types should be used in the dashboard for specific indicators, in particular whether to rely on historical climate observations, projections or a combination of both. This has delayed data preparation and complicated visualisation choices.

Impact on pilots: Slows indicator delivery and creates inconsistency across regions.

Linked Pilot Risks: 2.2

Mitigation:

- provide a clear decision tree for data selection (historical vs projected),
- explicitly link each indicator to its required data source (e.g. Euro-CORDEX, national services),
- include examples of correct implementation for each data category.

4.4. Difficulties with updating data (no API, manual data upload).

Many regional datasets cannot be accessed programmatically and lack APIs, forcing partners to rely on manual downloads and uploads. The workflow remains largely manual and fragmented.

The risk of using outdated data increases, each update cycle requires substantial time and options for automation or near real-time integration are limited. This reduces the long-term scalability and sustainability of the dashboard.

Impact on pilots: Reduces scalability and long-term usability, and can weaken addenda evidence if data ages out.

Linked Pilot Risks: 2.2

Mitigation:

- focus on datasets with reliable update cycles,
- explore semi-automated solutions where feasible

4.5. Limited or delayed data delivery

Some partners delivered datasets or metadata later than planned or in formats that required substantial cleaning. Internal deadlines were often soft or not clearly communicated.

Testing and debugging phases were shortened, user validation sessions were delayed and the risk of errors in pilot planning and addenda development increased. CSI and other technical partners had less time to verify and correct issues.

Impact on pilots: Shortens testing/debugging; delays validation sessions; increases error risk in pilot planning and addenda work.

Linked Pilot Risks: 2.1, 2.3

Mitigation:

- introduce firm internal deadlines for data delivery, aligned with dashboard development milestones
- require partners to pre-check completeness and formatting,
- create a simple checklist for dataset submission to standardise the process

5. Stakeholder engagement

Stakeholder engagement is a core element of the Climate_CRICES methodology. This section focuses on practical challenges in reaching, engaging and retaining stakeholders, and how these issues weaken the evidence base for pilots and addenda.

5.1. Low interest from local community in taking part in project activities

In many regions, local communities show limited interest in project activities. Climate adaptation is perceived as abstract or distant, awareness of data-driven planning is low, workshop timing often clashes with local events or work schedules and communication channels to non-expert groups are weak.

As a result, the range of perspectives captured in workshops is narrow, understanding of local vulnerabilities is incomplete and the legitimacy of workshop conclusions is weaker than intended. Some social groups and local concerns remain underrepresented in the evidence base.

Impact on pilots: Narrow perspectives, underrepresented concerns, weaker legitimacy of workshop conclusions.

Linked Pilot Risks: 3.2, 3.3

Mitigation:

- use targeted communication tailored to local communities and their information channels
- frame workshops around concrete, relatable impacts such as heatwaves, floods or droughts
- work more closely with municipalities and NGOs to extend outreach beyond expert circles

5.2. Difficulties engaging citizens and local actors (low motivation, limited availability)

Some stakeholder groups such as farmers, local NGOs and vulnerable communities are hard to reach and even harder to keep involved. Time constraints and a low perceived relevance of climate planning to everyday work are the main barriers.

Key user groups are underrepresented, the picture of adaptation barriers is incomplete and the likelihood that dashboard outputs will be used in practice decreases. Project results risk remaining confined to institutional stakeholders.

Impact on pilots: Underrepresentation of key users; reduced likelihood of real use of dashboard and pilot outputs.

Linked Pilot Risks: 3.1, 3.4, 4.3

Mitigation:

- engage intermediaries (chambers, associations),
- offer hybrid or shorter workshop formats,
- highlight practical benefits (e.g. risk reduction, funding opportunities).

5.3. Low attendance at stakeholder workshops, leading to incomplete understanding of local needs.

Despite broad invitations, several workshops had lower than expected attendance. In some cases, invitations were sent too late, overlapped with other events or did not clearly explain the purpose and benefits of participation.

Qualitative input is limited and the resulting picture of regional needs is partial. Opportunities for genuine co-creation are reduced, and the evidence base for indicator design and pilot planning is weaker.

Impact on pilots: Partial qualitative inputs; weaker evidence base for indicator design and pilot planning.

Linked Pilot Risks: 3.1, 3.4,

Mitigation:

- increase pre-workshop outreach and reminder cycles,
- invite stakeholders earlier and secure commitments,
- adjust timing to local administrative calendars.

5.4. Difficulty reaching the appropriate target groups (weak outreach)

Partners reported difficulties in identifying and engaging the most relevant stakeholders, particularly for biodiversity impacts, cross-border issues and sector-specific data needs (water utilities, health agencies, etc.).

Mapping of regional adaptation processes remains incomplete, important data needs are not fully captured and there are gaps in validating indicators or pilot focus areas. Some sectors that are critical for implementation are only weakly involved.

Impact on pilots: Gaps in validating indicators and defining pilot focus; incomplete mapping of processes and data needs.

Linked Pilot Risks: 3.1, 3.4, 4.3

Mitigation:

- refine stakeholder mapping
- use snowball sampling through engaged stakeholders,
- involve regional coordinators (e.g. Euroregion, planning agencies) as connectors.

5.5. Stakeholder fatigue.

In some areas, stakeholders show clear signs of workshop fatigue due to multiple events in a short period, overlapping regional or EU-funded initiatives and repeated requests for similar information.

Attendance declines over time, contributions become shorter or less meaningful and willingness to engage in follow-up activities drops. This undermines continuity of dialogue and weakens trust in participatory processes.

Impact on pilots: Reduced continuity and trust; weaker follow-up participation (testing, validation, addendum consultations).

Linked Pilot Risks: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5

Mitigation:

- coordinate timing with other regional events,
- merge objectives of multiple sessions when possible,
- provide clear added value (e.g. tailored conclusions, data products).

6. Training effectiveness

Training activities link the technical work of WP1 with the practical needs of pilot actions. Their purpose is to ensure that local and regional actors can use the dashboard, interpret indicators and apply data-driven principles in adaptation planning. At this stage, planning

is already advanced, so the focus is on stabilising the training concept, improving the remaining sessions and avoiding the same issues in future tasks.

6.1. Low interest of target users in dashboard-based training activities.

In some regions, interest in dashboard-focused trainings has been low. Main reasons include an overloaded information landscape, limited digital skills among some stakeholders, weak perceived relevance to daily work and low awareness of what the dashboard can actually offer.

Sessions attract fewer participants and generate only limited feedback for improving the tool. There is a risk that the dashboard remains underused or confined to a small group of technically inclined users, while the wider target groups stay passive observers.

Impact on pilots: Fewer participants and limited feedback; dashboard risks being underused.

Linked Pilot Risks: 3.2, 3.3

Mitigation:

- reframe trainings around concrete, local questions
- offer short introductory formats before extended trainings,
- work with municipalities and agencies to embed trainings into existing meetings instead of organising stand alone events

6.2. Lack of a clearly defined aim of the training.

WP2.1 training activities initially did not have a clearly defined objective. The description in the Application Form left room for different interpretations. Partners were unsure whether the focus should be on dashboard functionalities, interpretation of indicators, methodological aspects of pilot planning, or a combination of these elements.

This made it difficult to design the content and align trainings with pilot needs. Discussions often revolved around how each partner understood the idea rather than how to implement it in practice.

Impact on pilots: Training content hard to align with pilot needs and data literacy demands.

Linked Pilot Risks: 6

Mitigation:

- agree a short, written training concept that specifies 2 - 3 core aims for WP2.1, validated with pilot leaders
- derive the remaining training modules directly from these aims and from concrete pilot use cases, not from abstract debates
- use this concept as a reference point for closing open discussions, while keeping flexibility for regional adaptations

6.3. Lack of strategic alignment between trainings and pilot actions (training-pilot mismatch)

The Application Form described training and pilot work separately, and the link between them was not operationalised early on. As a result, early training plans did not systematically reflect the specific competencies needed for pilots, such as working with heat and drought indicators, flood risk layers or biodiversity metrics. Trainings risked remaining generic, while pilots required more targeted skills and data literacy.

Impact on pilots: Training stays generic while pilots require specific capabilities.

Linked Pilot Risks: 6

Mitigation:

- for each pilot, identify 1 - 2 concrete training topics that support its implementation and integrate them into the remaining training plan
- each pilot team should contribute at least one use case or dataset to be used in training exercises, instead of expecting central content delivery

6.4. Unclear Division of Responsibilities for Training Programme and Materials.

Partners reported uncertainty over who should develop the training programme, prepare didactic materials, deliver sessions and evaluate outcomes. In practice, many tasks were implicitly shifted to WP Leader, even though training content should be adapted to regional situations and built on local examples.

Preparation work became fragmented and slow, and some partners remained in a waiting position, repeatedly asking for detailed instructions. This increased the workload for the WP leader without a proportional gain in content quality.

Impact on pilots: Fragmented preparation, waiting behaviour, increased WP leader workload with low gain in quality.

Linked Pilot Risks: 6

Mitigation:

- clarify, which elements are prepared centrally (overall concept, common templates) and which are the responsibility of each partner (regional agenda, examples, materials)
- require each partner to develop at least a minimal set of their own materials
- use a simple planning sheet that lists, per region, who is responsible for programme design, materials, delivery and evaluation

7. Cross-border Cooperation (Tri-border Area)

In the tri-border area of Poland, Germany and Czechia several bottlenecks limit effective cross-border collaboration and reduce the project's potential to support integrated climate adaptation in the Nysa region. This section outlines the main institutional and practical barriers.

7.1. Low motivation for tri-border cooperation in the Nysa region

Stakeholders tend to prioritise local agendas and show limited interest in cross-border processes that do not bring visible, immediate local benefits. This is particularly evident among local-level actors, who perceive climate risks primarily through a municipal rather than regional or trilateral lens.

As a result, engagement in joint workshops is weaker, inputs for shared indicators and data needs are limited, and there is a clear risk that pilots remain fragmented instead of regionally coordinated. Opportunities for joint solutions and coordinated measures along the Nysa are underused.

Impact on pilots: Weaker joint engagement, fewer inputs for shared indicators, risk of fragmented pilots and symbolic cross-border content.

Linked Pilot Risks: 4.1, 4.3

Mitigation:

- emphasise concrete, mutual benefits of trilateral cooperation for each side
- design joint activities that produce visible short-term value for each side.

7.2. Language barriers hindering joint workshops and communication.

Workshops and cross-border exchanges are constrained by language differences. The need for simultaneous translation or bilingual materials slows discussions, complicates facilitation and increases organisational effort.

Impact on pilots: Reduced workshop quality and effectiveness of cross-border exchanges.

Linked Pilot Risks: 4.1, 4.3, 4.5

Mitigation:

- prepare bilingual materials in advance,
- offer simultaneous translation for key meetings,
- use visual tools (maps, diagrams, dashboards) to support multilingual dialogue.

7.3. Lack of clarity on how to operationalise trilateral cooperation.

Although the need for joint action is broadly recognised, there is no shared operational roadmap for cross-border work in the Nysa area. Leadership, task division, result-sharing arrangements and coordination mechanisms across three separate administrative and political systems remain unclear.

This lack of structure increases the risk of delays in pilot implementation, reduces the impact of cross-border activities and makes it harder to embed results in local adaptation plans or present a coherent trilateral narrative in the addenda.

Impact on pilots: Delays, reduced impact, weak embedding in plans, weak trilateral narrative

Linked Pilot Risks: 4.1, 4.4

Mitigation:

- co develop a clear operational framework for trilateral work (roles, responsibilities, workflows),
- set shared milestones and expected outputs for the Nysa area
- leverage existing cross-border structures (Euroregion Nysa/Nisa/Neisse).

8. Development of addenda

Addenda are key project outputs intended to update existing climate adaptation plans using data analysis, dashboard results and pilot work, so that regional strategies are revised on an evidence-based basis. This section reviews the factors that limit the quality, timing and uptake of addenda, including access to policy processes, political cycles and data constraints.

8.1. Limited ability to develop meaningful addenda due to lack of access to policy processes.

In tri-border areas partners do not have direct access to formal policy-making processes. They often act as external experts or project implementers without a clear role in strategy revision or decision-making procedures.

As a result, addenda risk remaining purely advisory documents with limited impact on actual policy change. Their recommendations may not be seriously considered or formally adopted, and the long-term value of the project for local and regional authorities is harder to demonstrate.

Impact on pilots: Addenda risk remaining advisory only, with limited political consideration or adoption.

Linked Pilot Risks: 3.1, 5.1

Mitigation:

- identify key policy windows and align project actions accordingly,
- involve policy-makers early (e.g. through targeted briefings),
- use the dashboard as an entry point for dialogue with authorities.

8.2. Misalignment between political cycles and project timeline.

Local and regional strategy revision cycles often do not match the Climate_CRICES project timeline. Elections, changes in regional leadership or slow administrative procedures can easily push climate strategy updates beyond the project's end date.

Addenda may therefore not be formally discussed or approved while the project is still running. Pilot findings and dashboard results are only partially used, and there is a real risk that work on addenda loses momentum once project funding ends.

Impact on pilots: Addenda may not be discussed or approved during the project; momentum may drop after funding ends.

Linked Pilot Risks: 5.2

Mitigation:

- track political cycles in each region,
- prepare addenda in modular format for later adoption,
- ensure materials remain usable beyond the project lifetime.

8.3. Data incomplete or inconsistent.

Addenda depend strongly on the dashboard, on the availability and quality of indicators and on consistent datasets across regions. In some areas, biodiversity data are incomplete, hydrological inputs inconsistent or indicators missing.

This weakens the robustness and credibility of policy recommendations. Addenda may lack precision and operational value, policy-makers have less confidence in the findings and links between pilot results and broader adaptation strategies become less convincing.

Impact on pilots: Policy recommendations less trusted; weaker link between pilot results and strategy updates.

Linked Pilot Risks: 1.1, 5.4

Mitigation:

- present data gaps and uncertainties transparently within the addenda
- use alternative indicators where justified and methodologically sound
- include methodological annexes that explain data sources, limitations and assumptions

8.4 Lack of coherence across pilots (different indicators, formats)

Pilot regions use different indicator sets, data structures and thematic priorities. This reflects local conditions and institutional contexts but makes it harder to design a coherent addendum structure and to extract cross-regional insights.

Pilot outcomes are difficult to synthesise, recommendations are inconsistent and developing a unified policy narrative for the project as a whole is challenging. External readers may struggle to see how the pilots connect at a strategic level.

Impact on pilots: Cross-region narrative and comparability weaken; external readers struggle to understand project-level logic.

Linked Pilot Risks: 5.3, 5.5

Mitigation:

- provide a common addenda template with flexible sections,
- harmonise indicator lists as far as possible,
- highlight shared lessons while clearly distinguishing local specifics.

Table 1. Bottleneck summary

Category	Bottleneck / Issue	Impact on Project	Recommended Mitigation	Responsible Partners
Consortium coordination and operational clarity	Divergent interpretations of tasks, unclear instructions	Inconsistent deliverables; delays in WP1-WP3	Written summaries after meetings; clear templates; explicit instructions	WP leaders; All partners (document owners)
	Low responsiveness and delayed feedback	Slowed progress; repeated follow-up	Set deadlines; assign feedback roles; regular control calls	WP leaders; All partners (document owners)
	Insufficient feedback for pilot needs	Weak alignment with WP2	Structured feedback forms; targeted calls	WP2 leader + LP,; All partners
Capacity, workload and continuity	Overload of key partners (LP, CSI, task leaders)	Bottlenecks affecting multiple WPs	Delegate tasks; add support staff; workload monitoring	LP; CSI; WP leaders
	Skill asymmetry across partners	Uneven quality; increased burden on expert partners	Internal mentoring; template-based guidance	Experienced partners (CSI, IOER, RV, ARPA); WP leaders
	Staff turnover and knowledge loss	Delays; loss of continuity	Systematic documentation; shared responsibilities	LP, WP Leaders, All partners
Data Availability & Quality	Missing biodiversity & hydrological data	Missing indicators; inconsistent outputs	Use EU/global datasets; mark gaps transparently	WP1 leader; rel. WG leader
	Inconsistent formats & metadata	Additional cleaning needed	Standardised metadata template	WP1 leader, CSI
	Incompatible scales & georeferencing	Hard-to-compare indicators	Preferred scales; transformation guidance	WP1 leader, CSI, WG leaders
	Lack of indicator methods	Calculation inconsistencies	Method sheets; technical sessions	WP1 leader + WG Leaders
Dashboard Development & Workflow	Dashboard misaligned with local data availability	Incomplete indicators; reduced comparability	Minimum common denominator; clear marking of gaps	CSI; WP1 leader+Rel. PP
	Repeated metadata restructuring	Delays; technical inconsistencies	Freeze metadata model; detailed metadata guidance	CSI; WP1 leader + WG leads
	Uncertainty: historical vs projected data	Misaligned visualisations; slowed progress	Provide data selection decision tree	CSI; WP1 leader + WG leads
	Manual data updates (no APIs)	Outdated datasets; heavy workload	Document update cycles; use stable sources	CSI; WP1 leader + WG leads
	Delayed data delivery	Reduced testing time	Strict deadlines; dataset checklist	CSI; WP1 leader + WG leads

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Category	Bottleneck / Issue	Impact on Project	Recommended Mitigation	Responsible Partners
Stakeholder Engagement	Low community interest	Limited insights; weak legitimacy	Stronger outreach; relatable examples	CDDA; All partners
	Difficulty engaging key actors	Underrepresentation; missing data needs	Intermediary organisations; flexible formats	All partners
	Low workshop attendance	Incomplete SWOT & needs mapping	Early invitations; reminders; timing adaptation	All partners
	Stakeholder fatigue	Declining engagement	Merge events; clarify added value	PP05 (communication manager) + PP08 (WP2 lead)+ All PPs
Training Activity	Unclear aim of trainings	Misaligned expectations	Define learning outcomes; unified syllabus	LP +WP2 lead + Communication Manager
	Training-pilot mismatch	Reduced usefulness for pilots	Co-design with pilot leaders	WG leaders
	Unclear responsibilities	Delays; uneven material quality	Clear task allocation; shared plan	WP2 lead + WG leaders + All PPs
	Low interest among users	Low turnout	Short intro sessions; show practical benefits	Training organisers
Cross-border Cooperation	Low motivation for trilateral cooperation	Limited engagement; fragmented outputs	Emphasise benefits; co-create shared milestones	Regional partners (DE-PL-CZ)
	Language barriers	Reduced workshop quality	Bilingual materials; translation support	Regional partners (DE-PL-CZ))
	Lack of operational roadmap for trilateral work	Delays in pilot activities	Develop clear workflow; use Euroregion structures	Regional partners (DE-PL-CZ)
Addenda & Policy Integration	Limited access to policy processes	Addenda may remain advisory	Early engagement of policy-makers	WG leaders, All partners
	Misalignment with political cycles	Low adoption likelihood	Prepare modular addenda; track cycles	All partners, WP2 Leader
	Data gaps lower addenda quality	Reduced credibility	Transparent gaps; alternative indicators	WG leads+relevant PPs
	Lack of pilot coherence	Hard to synthesise findings	Common addenda template; harmonised indicators	WP2 leader, WG leaders

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D. 2.1.2 Report on the transborder climate change effects' projections to be analysed

ANNEX 2: Risk Register

Partner responsible: UPWr

Main Author: Anna Uciechowska-Grakowicz

Delivery Date: 28.02.2026

Risk register

Table 1. Risk Register

Category	Risk ID	Risk Title (short)	Risk Description	Level	Likelihood	Impact	Linked Bottleneck ID(s)	Bottleneck root cause	Mitigation Measures	Risk owner	Status	Notes
Data availability and indicators readiness	1.1	Lack of essential data	Lack of essential data, especially biodiversity projections, undermining the evidence base for pilots and addenda.	Project	High	High	B3.1, B8.3	Missing biodiversity/hydrological data; data gaps lower addenda quality.	Use EU/global datasets where justified; Define fallback indicators; Document gaps and assumptions;	WP1 leader + relevant WG lead + relevant PP		
	1.2	Missing datasets for key indicators	Missing datasets for key indicators (heat, flood, biodiversity) prevent producing or comparing core pilot indicators.	Project	High	High	B3.1, B4.1, B3.3	Data gaps; dashboard misfit to local availability; incompatible scales.	Agree minimum indicator set; Define preferred scales and transformations; allow justified alternative indicators; Mark partial coverage.	WP1 leader, relevant WG lead, CSI		

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	1.3	Incompatible scales/georeferencing	Incompatible spatial/temporal scales and georeferencing reduce comparability across pilots and cross-border outputs.	Project	Medium	High	B3.3, B4.1	Incompatible scales and georeferencing; uneven data availability.	Agree preferred scales per indicator; provide aggregation/resampling guidance; require spatial relevance validation.	WP1 leader+CSI + WG leads		
	1.4	Lack of indicator methods	Lack of indicator calculation rules leads to inconsistent results and undermines credibility of pilot evidence.	Project	Medium	High	B3.4	Missing indicator methods; inconsistent calculations.	Prepare method sheets per indicator; publish assumptions/limits; technical sessions to align calculations.	WP1 leader + WG Leaders		
Dashboard delivery and data workflow	2.1	Dashboard deployment delays	Delays in deploying the dashboard prevent testing and referencing it in pilot outputs and addenda.	Project	High	High	B2.1, B4.2, B4.5, B1.3	Overload of key partners; repeated metadata restructuring; delayed data delivery; delayed feedback.	staged releases; definition of pilot-critical features; aligned dependencies between WP outputs. regular technical checkpoints.	LP + WP leads + CSI		
	2.2	Dynamic data not integrated	Dynamic data cannot be integrated into the dashboard, causing indicators to become outdated or unavailable.	Project	High	High	B4.4, B4.3, B4.1	Manual updates/no API; historical vs projections uncertainty; dashboard misfit to local data.	Define refreshable vs static indicators; document update cycles; timestamp outputs; decision tree for historical vs projections.	CSI + WP1 lead + WG Leads		

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	2.3	Late or incomplete data delivery	Late or incomplete data delivery to the dashboard leads to incomplete evidence and weakened pilot outputs.	Project	High	High	B4.5, B1.3	Delayed data delivery; delayed feedback.	Firm internal deadlines; dataset checklist; named owners per dataset; escalation path for slips.	al PPs: person resp. for data input + CSI + WP1 lead + WG Leads		
	2.4	No metadata / heterogeneous data	Heterogeneous or unstructured data without metadata leads to inconsistent indicator logic and gaps.	Project	High	High	B1.2, B4.2	Inconsistent formats/metadata; repeated metadata restructuring; unclear instructions.	Mandatory metadata template; validation before ingestion; freeze metadata model after consolidation.	CSI + WG leaders		
Stakeholder and participation risks	3.1	Low engagement from authorities	Low engagement from local authorities reduces pilot relevance, validation quality, and uptake potential.	Partner	High	High	B5.2, B5.3, B8.1	Difficulty engaging key actors; low workshop attendance; limited access to policy processes.	Use intermediaries; earlier invitations; role-specific messaging; short targeted briefings; hybrid formats.	WG leads + relevant PPs		
	3.2	Information saturation	Information saturation leads to low interest in adaptation data, limiting stakeholder contributions to pilots/addenda.	Partner	High	High	B5.1, B6.4, B5.4	Low community interest; low training interest; fatigue.	Curate a small indicator set per audience; provide short summaries; show practical decisions supported by data; avoid data dumping.	PP05 (communication manager) +WP2 lead+ All PPs		
	3.3	Low interest in dashboard	Limited stakeholder interest in the dashboard and its data reduces feedback and usefulness for pilots.	Partner	High	Medium	B6.4, B5.1	Low user interest; low community interest.	Intro sessions with local use cases; exportable outputs for their reports; clarify benefits per stakeholder type.	CDDA, All PPs		

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	3.4	Too few validators	Too few engaged stakeholders to validate addenda reduces legitimacy and regional fit.	Partner	High	High	B5.3, B5.2, B5.4	Low attendance; difficulty engaging; fatigue.	Expand outreach; snowball sampling; smaller targeted sessions; asynchronous validation; document dissenting views.	PP05 (communication manager) +WP2 lead+ All PPs		
	3.5	Stakeholder fatigue	Stakeholder fatigue due to excessive meeting demand lowers participation in consultations and testing.	Partner	High	Medium	B5.4	Fatigue from too many events/initiatives.	Merge events; reduce repetition; clear value per session; rotate formats; asynchronous feedback options.	PP05 (communication manager) +WP2 lead+ All PPs		
Cross-border cooperation risks	4.1	Low cross-border motivation	Low motivation for cross-border cooperation (PL-DE-CZ) weakens cross-border pilot outputs and addenda content.	Partner	High	High	B7.1, B7.3, B7.2	Low motivation; no operational roadmap; language barriers.	Emphasise mutual benefits; co-create shared milestones; leverage Euroregion structures; visible short-term value.	PP07+PP08 +PP09		
	4.2	No transborder projections	Dashboard cannot support transborder projections, so tri-border outputs lack comparable evidence.	Project	Medium	High	B4.1, B3.3, B3.4	Dashboard misfit; incompatible scales; missing methods.	Minimum common indicator set; transformation guidance; mark gaps; method sheets for calculations.	PP07+PP08 +PP09 + CSI		
	4.3	Low tri-border stakeholder engagement	Low engagement of local stakeholders in the tri-border pilot reduces cross-border validation and shared needs definition.	Partner	High	High	B7.1, B7.2, B5.2	Low motivation; language barriers; difficulty engaging key actors.	Targeted communication; bilateral pre-meetings; benefit framing; translation support; visual tools (maps/dashboard).	PP07+PP08 +PP09		

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	4.4	No trilateral operational roadmap	Lack of an operational roadmap for trilateral work causes unclear roles/workflow, delays, and fragmented outputs.	Partner	High	High	B7.3, B1.1	No operational roadmap; divergent interpretations.	Co-develop operational framework; define roles/workflow/milestones; leverage Euroregion structures.	PP07+PP08 +PP09 + WP2 lead		
	4.5	Language barriers	Language barriers reduce workshop quality and slow cross-border coordination, weakening shared outputs.	Partner	Medium	Medium	B7.2	Translation needs and communication friction.	Bi/trilingual materials; translation support for key meetings; plan facilitation; use visual tools.	PP07+PP08 +PP09		
Uptake and institutional embedding	5.1	Limited ability to adopt addenda	Limited institutional ability to create or adopt addenda blocks political consideration and uptake.	Partner	Medium	High	B8.1	Limited access to policy processes.	Engage policymakers early; map adoption pathway; align structure to procedures; use dashboard as dialogue entry point.	Relevant WG lead (PP09/PP08/PP04) + all PPs		
	5.2	Political cycle misalignment	Political cycles misaligned with addendum timeline reduce chance of formal discussion/adoption during project lifetime.	Partner	Medium	High	B8.2	Political cycle timing constraints.	Track cycles; prepare modular outputs for later adoption; ensure materials usable beyond project lifetime.	WP2 lead + relevant PPs		

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	5.3	Addendum seen as too generic	Overgeneralisation of addenda across diverse contexts leads to perception of generic guidelines and weak local adoption.	Project	Medium	Medium	B8.4, B1.1	Lack of coherence across pilots; divergent expectations.	Common template with flexible local annexes; distinguish shared lessons vs local specifics; justify deviations.	WP2 lead + WG leads		
	5.4	Low-quality addenda due to data gaps	Data gaps and inconsistency lead to low-quality addenda, reducing credibility and policymaker confidence.	Project	Medium	High	B8.3, B3.1, B3.2	Data gaps and missing metadata reduce addenda quality.	Transparent gaps/uncertainties; alternative indicators where justified; methodological annex with sources/limits/assumptions.	All PPs + WG leads (PP09/PP08/PP04)		
	5.5	Lack of coherence across pilots	Different indicators and formats across pilots weaken synthesis and project-wide narrative and structure.	Project	Medium	High	B8.4, B3.4, B1.1	Pilot coherence issues; missing indicator methods; divergent expectations.	Common addenda template; harmonise indicator lists where possible; clearly separate shared vs local-specific lessons.	Relevant WG lead (PP09/PP08/PP04)		
Training	6	Unclear training objectives/responsibilities	Lack of clarity about training objectives and responsibilities reduces training effectiveness and delays downstream pilot work.	Project	Medium	High	B6.1, B6.2, B6.3	Unclear training aim; mismatch to pilot needs; unclear responsibilities.	Define learning outcomes and syllabus; clarify central vs regional responsibilities; co-design with pilot leaders; planning sheet per region.	WP2 lead+Communication Manager+LP		
Consortium operations	7.1	Overload of key partners	Overload of key partners (LP, CSI, WP leaders) delays pilot-critical outputs (methods, training, dashboard integration).	Project	High	High	B2.1	Concentration of tasks on few partners.	Delegate tasks; add support capacity; monitor workload; redistribute review burden; clarify acceptance criteria.	LP + WP leads + CSI		

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7.2	Unclear outputs and divergent interpretations	Divergent interpretations of tasks/templates and unclear instructions cause rework, inconsistent deliverables, and delays.	Project	High	High	B1.1, B1.2	Divergent interpretations; unclear instructions.	Written summaries after meetings; embed instructions in templates; examples of correct outputs; shared glossary.	WP leads + document owners		
7.3	Delayed feedback	Low responsiveness and delayed feedback compress timelines, delay decisions, and slow iteration cycles needed for pilots.	Project	High	High	B1.3	Delayed feedback and responsiveness.	Explicit feedback deadlines; assign reviewers; regular control calls; reminders/shared calendars; escalation path.	WP leads + LP + all partners		
7.4	Skill asymmetry	Skill asymmetry across partners increases burden on experts, slows consolidation, and reduces harmonisation.	Project	Medium	High	B2.2, B2.1	Uneven competencies and overload of experts.	Internal mentoring; planned verification rounds; strict templates and examples; allocate time for revision.	LP + WP leads + CSI		
7.5	Turnover and single-person dependency	Staff turnover and single-person dependency cause continuity loss, delays, and repeated decisions.	Partner	Medium	High	B2.3	Turnover and knowledge loss; low redundancy.	Systematic documentation; handover procedure; central knowledge repository; ensure at least two active staff per key role.	LP + WP leads + all partners		

Pilot timing	8	Unclear pilot timing	Lack of clarity on timing of the relevant pilot action causes misalignment of engagement, data delivery, and drafting.	Partner	Medium	Medium	B1.1, B1.3, B5.3	Coordination issues; delayed feedback; workshop attendance constraints.	Single shared pilot timeline; confirm dates at WP level; treat changes as managed change requests; written summaries.	WP2 lead (PP08) + WG leaders + LP		
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Table 2. Bottleneck-risk dependency

Bottleneck ID	Bottleneck Title	Description	Mitigation owner	Linked Risk IDs
B1.1	Divergent interpretations of tasks/templates	Different understandings of scope/format; weak written follow-up after meetings.	WP leads, document owners	4.4, 5.3, 5.5, 7.2, 8
B1.2	Lack of clear operational instructions	Missing step-by-step guidance and examples; uncertainty about expected outputs.	WP leads, document owners	2.4, 7.2
B1.3	Low responsiveness and delayed feedback	Late feedback due to workload and unclear deadlines; slows iteration cycles.	LP + WP leads + all partners	2.1, 2.3, 7.3, 8
B2.1	Overload of key partners and task leaders	Concentration of advanced tasks on few people/partners; cascading delays.	LP + WP leads + CSI	2.1, 7.1, 7.4
B2.2	Skill asymmetry across partners	Uneven competencies increase review/correction burden and slow consolidation.	LP + WP leads + all partners	7.4
B2.3	Staff turnover / single-person dependency	Loss of know-how, delays, repeated discussions; low delivery resilience.	LP + WP leads + all partners	7.5
B3.1	Missing biodiversity and hydrological data	Weak data coverage; missing authoritative datasets and projections.	WP1 leader + relevant WG lead	1.1, 1.2, 5.4
B3.2	Inconsistent formats and missing metadata	Multiple formats; incomplete metadata (coverage, methods, units, assumptions).	WP1 leader+CSI	5.4
B3.3	Incompatible spatial/temporal scales	Different resolutions, CRS, boundaries; comparability challenges.	WP1 leader+CSI + WG leads	1.2, 1.3, 4.2
B3.4	Lack of indicator methods	Missing calculation rules and method sheets; inconsistent results risk.	WP1 leader + WG Leaders	1.4, 4.2, 5.5
B4.1	Dashboard not adapted to local data availability	Regional differences in data completeness complicate common dashboard structure.	PP07/CSI + relevant PPs	1.2, 1.3, 2.2, 4.2
B4.2	Repeated metadata restructuring	Iterative changes to metadata model; increases workload and delays.	PP07/CSI + WG leaders	2.1, 2.4
B4.3	Uncertainty: historical vs projected data usage	Unclear rules for observations vs projections; delays preparation/visualisation.	PP07/CSI + WG leaders	2.2
B4.4	Manual updates (no API)	Datasets cannot be accessed programmatically; manual uploads; outdated data risk.	PP07/CSI + WG leaders	2.2
B4.5	Delayed data delivery to dashboard	Late datasets/metadata; heavy cleaning; unclear internal deadlines.	PP07/CSI + WG leaders	2.1, 2.3
B5.1	Low community interest	Adaptation seen as abstract; low awareness; weak channels; timing conflicts.	CDDA, All PPs	3.2, 3.3
B5.2	Difficulty engaging key actors	Hard-to-reach stakeholders; limited availability; low perceived relevance.	All PPs	3.1, 3.4, 4.3
B5.3	Low workshop attendance	Late invitations, scheduling clashes, unclear value proposition.	All PPs	3.1, 3.4, 8
B5.4	Stakeholder fatigue	Too many events/initiatives; declining engagement quality over time.	PP05 (CM) +WP2 lead+ All PPs	3.2, 3.4, 3.5
B6.1	Unclear aim of trainings	Training objectives not clear; debates rather than implementation.	LP +WP2 lead+PP05(CM)	6

B6.2	Training-pilot mismatch	Training stays generic while pilots need targeted skills and use cases.	WG leaders	6
B6.3	Unclear responsibilities for training materials	Uncertainty over who prepares/delivers/evaluates training; tasks drift to leaders.	WP2 lead + WG leaders + All PPs	6
B6.4	Low interest among users in dashboard-based training	Low perceived relevance or limited digital skills; weak uptake of training.	All PPs	3.2, 3.3
B7.1	Low motivation for trilateral cooperation	Stakeholders prioritise local agendas; limited perceived cross-border benefit.	PP07+PP08+PP09	4.1, 4.3
B7.2	Language barriers	Translation needs slow facilitation and increase organisational load.	PP07+PP08+PP09	4.1, 4.3, 4.5
B7.3	No operational trilateral roadmap	No shared framework for roles, workflow, milestones, outputs across three systems.	PP07+PP08+PP09	4.1, 4.4
B8.1	Limited access to policy processes	Partners may act as external experts without clear role in formal strategy revision.	WG leads + relevant PPs	3.1, 5.1
B8.2	Misalignment with political cycles	Elections/strategy cycles exceed project timeline; adoption windows missed.	WP2 lead + relevant PPs	5.2
B8.3	Data gaps lower addenda quality	Incomplete/inconsistent data reduces credibility and operational value of addenda.	WG leads+relevant PPs	1.1, 5.4
B8.4	Lack of coherence across pilots	Different indicators/formats make synthesis and unified structure difficult.	WP2+WG leads (PP09, PP08, PP04)	5.3, 5.5

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D. 2.1.2 Report on the transborder climate change effects' projections to be analysed

ANNEX 3: Project Partners' work plans

Partner responsible: UPWr

Main Author: Anna Uciechowska-Grakowicz

Delivery Date: 28.02.2026

Regional work plans

LP01+PP02 Regional work plan

Which Pilot Action(s) PP is involved in

The Pilot Action aims to enhance the expertise of regional climate change professionals. By using the project Dashboard, the goal is to improve the ability to plan a climate-ready territory, providing concrete support to local authorities and stakeholders in managing drought and heatwaves impacts. In particular, the aims are the followings:

- supporting the application of the Regional Climate Change Adaptation Strategy, by providing practical instruments and guidelines (Dashboard);
- fostering the accessibility of data and indicators, by organizing and making regional climate platforms easy to use for technical assessments;
- monitoring the advancement of adaptation measures, by making accessible the progress status of measures planned under the SRACC and by clearly identifying responsible departments, taking advantage of the Dashboard response Indicators.

What type of addendum or contribution is realistically feasible in PPs context

The Addendum is intended as a document to provide the technical support needed to integrate the Strategy's knowledge framework. In particular, it may include:

- specific climatological study with respect to drought and heatwaves hazards in Veneto by considering the historical 1991-2025 period and the projections until 2100; this study is designed to enhance the Veneto Climate Framework for the SRACC implementation;
- operational tools to facilitate access for local technicians to hydro-climatic data, adaptation measures and response indicators with a specific focus on the Climate_CRICES Dashboard, and other official climate data platforms (e.g. CliNE platform, Thredds, SECURE Rainyapp, thematic section of Arpav website);
- improvement of operational bulletins for regional climate monitoring (monthly meteo-climate reports, and water resource reports) with the identification of new climate indicators and a more detailed explanation of the calculation methods.

Key dependencies or constraints (for example data gaps, technical problems, legal constraints, timing) that may hinder the Pilot Actions

There is a problem of updating the data within the Dashboard, that could be solved by updating the platforms which the Dashboard refers to. Another problem is related to the difficulty of involving the stakeholders. With regard to stakeholders, one difficulty is structuring training activities while taking into account that they have different levels of skill in using specialized data and platforms.

Stakeholders who will consult and validate addenda, plan for cooperation

Veneto Region will validate addenda

The stakeholders are:

- internal Stakeholders: Veneto Region Technical representatives from various Regional Departments: Environmental & Territory (Environmental Assessment, Soil & Coast Defense, Environment & Ecological Transition, Spatial Planning); Resources & Infrastructure (Agri-food, Forestry, Tourism, Infrastructure & Transport, Public Works); Safety & Innovation (Civil Protection, Prevention & Health, ICT & Digital Agenda, Research & Energy Innovation); Governance (Legal Support, Unitary Programming, Control Systems (SISTAR));
- external Stakeholders with respect to the Water & Land Management, including River Basin Authorities, Land Reclamation Consortia, and water resource management agencies.

A work schedule that includes peer to peer collaboration between regions

Conduct an overview of the platforms for climatological data presented by the project partners in Eisenstadt, which can be proposed to internal stakeholders for evaluation of data organization or as examples of best practices.

PP03 Regional work plan

Which Pilot Action(s) PP is involved in

CSI will deploy Pilot Actions 1 and 2 on Improving climate change adaptation plans focusing on heat and drought's effects and water shortage and flooding

What type of addendum or contribution is realistically feasible in PPs context

Addendums in the Piedmont pilots will most likely focus on possible integration proposals to the Regional Strategy on Climate Change that covers the topics related to both Pilot Actions

Key dependencies or constraints (for example data gaps, technical problems, legal constraints, timing) that may hinder the Pilot Actions

The activity in Piedmont is much dependant on the availability and regional stakeholders, that have demonstrated some interest in the project activities, but not much actual contributions

Stakeholders who will consult and validate addenda, plan for cooperation

The addenda will be elaborated and presented for validation to the Environment, Energy and Territory Department of the Piedmont Region

A work schedule that includes peer to peer collaboration between regions

Meetings are currently taking place with Piedmont Region stakeholders to stimulate interest in different sectors of the Environment Department, as well as the Agriculture department. We are also looking forward to hearing about progress and feedback from partners from other regions, to evaluate the possibility of integrating their knowledge and experience into the Piedmont territory.

PP04 Regional Work Plan

Which Pilot Action(s) PP is involved in

PP04 is involved in all three Pilot Actions (PA1, PA2, PA3) and acts as Working Group Lead for PA3 (biodiversity loss).

What type of addendum or contribution is realistically feasible in PPs context

In PP's context, a realistically feasible contribution would be a technical support document that embeds the Climate_CRICES dashboard (data, measures and indicators) as an operational tool. This document could be used either as an annex or as direct input to the planned Climate Strategy 2040 of Burgenland. In addition, it could also be attached as an annex to the existing concepts of the Climate Change Adaptation Regions (CCAR/KLAR).

Key dependencies or constraints (for example data gaps, technical problems, legal constraints, timing) that may hinder the Pilot Actions

Constraints are missing biodiversity projection datasets and unclear data updating workflows for the dashboard.

Stakeholders who will consult and validate addenda, plan for cooperation

There are plans to work with representatives of the state government of various departments: Energy & Climate Protection, Soil, Agriculture, Water and Civil Protection, Prevention & Health, and politicians at the Kick-off event for the Pilot Actions on the 26th of February. In spring 2026 there are plans for further online-meetings with those stakeholders. Another event will happen in March 2026 with the managers of the Climate Change Adaptation Regions (CCAR) of Burgenland and representatives of the CCAR-municipalities, as well as with representatives

of Burgenland's nature parks, including biodiversity experts. In addition, there are plans to reach out to other stakeholders through events such as the Long Night of Research on the 24th of April in Eisenstadt.

A work schedule that includes peer to peer collaboration between regions

The meeting mentioned above with the managers of the Climate Change Adaptation Regions (CCAR) of Burgenland and representatives of the CCAR-municipalities will be organized in March 2026. There are 3 CCARs in Burgenland, which are divided into 2 CCARs in the Northern Part and 1 in the South of Burgenland with quite different landscapes and meteorological differences. Also the representatives of Burgenland's nature parks, including many biodiversity experts, are coming from different regional parts of Burgenland, which makes a good peer to peer collaboration with different scenic and meteorological backgrounds.

PP05 Regional Work plan

Which Pilot Action(s) PP is involved in,

In the pilot action, CDDA (PP05) assesses the regional practice and future opportunities of data-based climate adaptation planning, as well as the possibilities and methods of using the dashboard in a specific area that is particularly vulnerable to climate change: viticulture and winemaking. The pilot action assesses the effects of all three climate change impacts studied within the framework of Climate_CRICES (heat and drought, flood, loss of biodiversity) on viticulture and winemaking.

What type of addendum or contribution is realistically feasible in PPs context,

The addendum planned by CDDA (PP05) will contain a situation analysis, adaptation goals, and measures to achieve them for each of the three climate change impacts covered by Climate_CRICES (heat and drought; flood; loss of biodiversity) for the Central Danube Region. The addendum will be compiled in such a way that it could be incorporated into the Operational Program for the Central Danube Priority Area without any further preparatory work during its upcoming review.

The addendum will be based partly on the results of pilot activities (identifying the needs of local stakeholders), partly on data and information available in the dashboard, and partly on data available in Hungarian databases.

Key dependencies or constraints (for example data gaps, technical problems, legal constraints, timing) that may hinder the Pilot Actions

There are two main factors that could hinder the successful implementation of pilot action in the Central Danube Region. The most important of these is that the focus of interest of stakeholders in the field of viticulture, which is the subject of the pilot action, is currently on a rapidly spreading grape disease in the Central Danube Region, which may lead to less interest in climate change as a broader topic. However, given that this disease is also linked to climate change, we believe that local stakeholders will also find the thematic focus of the pilot action interesting. Another risk factor in the implementation of the pilot activity is possible further delays in the preparation of the dashboard. In this case, the implementation of pilot action may be postponed.

Stakeholders who will consult and validate addenda, plan for cooperation

We would like to involve research institutes, universities, vineyards, climate change experts, and officials from interested local governments in the validation of the addendum.

A work schedule that includes peer to peer collaboration between regions.

The kick-off meeting for the pilot activities is scheduled for February 25, 2026. This will be followed by further workshops involving local stakeholders in the spring of 2026. As part of the pilot action, we aim to familiarize local vineyards and self-governments of vineyards (mountain communities) with the availability and use of climate change databases, in particular the dashboard. Another important goal is to encourage the development of regional partnerships that will exist even after Climate_CRICES has ended and serve as a consultation forum for discussing climate change related challenges and possible solutions in viticulture. We plan to conclude the pilot activity with a workshop in mid-April 2026. The CDDA plans to prepare the addendum using the results of the pilot action by early May 2026.

PP06 Regional Work Plan

Which Pilot Action(s) PP is involved in,

PP06 is involved in three Pilot Actions: PA1 (heat and drought), PA2 (flooding), and PA3 (biodiversity) - for the pilot area the City of Zagreb

What type of addendum or contribution is realistically feasible in PPs context,

In our case, this would take the form of a document with a strong focus on data related to three key climate change impacts, clearly demonstrating why the implementation of adaptation measures is important. We also expect this document to be prepared in the

form of an annex. In this way, we would show that climate change impacts can be addressed and managed through appropriate adaptation measures.

Key dependencies or constraints (for example data gaps, technical problems, legal constraints, timing) that may hinder the Pilot Actions

The main difficulties that may arise include a loss of interest in the tool and its use. This may occur due to limited prior knowledge and a low motivation to learn new things. For this reason, it is important that the training sessions we organize are well-targeted, as otherwise they could have the opposite effect.

Another challenge we identify is the lack of time on both our side and the side of our stakeholders, which may make it difficult to coordinate activities in a way that enables broad participation. It is therefore essential to plan training sessions well in advance so that participants can fit them into their schedules.

Stakeholders who will consult and validate addenda, plan for cooperation

Cooperation in the preparation and validation of the addendum is primarily expected from the City of Zagreb's Office for Strategic Planning and Development (GEOS), the Faculty of Agriculture, and the Andrija Štampar Teaching Institute of Public Health. Within GEOS, we will collaborate with several experts with experience in spatial, meteorological and environmental data, as well as in adaptation and mitigation measures and the development of strategic action documents. From colleagues at the Faculty of Agriculture, we expect additional insights into environmental impacts, while from the Andrija Štampar Institute we anticipate contributions related to the impacts of climate change on human health.

A work schedule that includes peer to peer collaboration between regions.

Through further training sessions, for which our stakeholders have expressed strong interest and motivation, we will continue to raise the level of engagement and understanding of the Climate_CRICES dashboard. We also expect active participation from stakeholders during the trainings, allowing us to share their progress and feedback with partners from other regions. We believe that such exchange of experiences can be highly valuable and beneficial.

PP07 Regional Work Plan

Which Pilot Action(s) PP is involved in:

PP07 is involved in all three Pilot Actions (PA1, PA2, PA3)

What type of addendum or contribution is realistically feasible in PPs context:

PP07 will co-develop a tri-border addendum jointly with PP08 (UPWr) and PP09 (UJEP), focused on the Neisse/Nysa catchment context and on avoiding maladaptation caused by cross-border governance, methodological and data inconsistencies. This is consistent with the project logic where addenda can function as technical, evidence-first documents supporting (not replacing) existing strategies and plans, with flexible uptake pathways depending on the institutional mandate of associated partners.

Key dependencies or constraints (for example data gaps, technical problems, legal constraints, timing) that may hinder the Pilot Actions:

Planning cycle and formal update constraints: WFD / Flood Directive-driven instruments follow strict planning cycles and update rules that do not align neatly with the project timeframe. Saxony is currently developing their state-wide climate change adaptation plan that is due in parliament after the end of the Climate_CRICES project. Therefore, the addendum may be proposed as a voluntary technical reference rather than a formally annexed document, highlighting the maladaptation issues described.

Stakeholders who will consult and validate addenda, plan for cooperation:

Primary associated partner and key consultation counterpart in Germany are A05 Sächsisches Landesamt für Umwelt, Landwirtschaft und Geologie and A06 Sächsisches Staatsministerium für Energie, Klimaschutz, Umwelt und Landwirtschaft. Cooperation is ongoing to ensure the addendum is tailored to their planning needs and realistic uptake routes. A three-phased consultation process was devised as follows:

A work schedule that includes peer to peer collaboration between regions.

PP07 works in a joint tri-border setup with PP08 and PP09, including coordinated cross-border events and a shared addendum workflow supported by regular (bi-weekly) coordination meetings and division of responsibilities.

PP08 Regional Work Plan

Which Pilot Action(s) PP is involved in:

PP08 is involved in all three Pilot Actions (PA1, PA2, PA3) and acts as Working Group Lead for PA2 (flooding).

What type of addendum or contribution is realistically feasible in PPs context:

PP08 will co-develop a tri-border addendum jointly with PP07 (IOER) and PP09 (UJEP), focused on the Neisse/Nysa catchment context and on avoiding maladaptation caused by cross-border governance, methodological and data inconsistencies. This is consistent with the project logic where addenda can function as technical, evidence-first documents supporting (not replacing) existing strategies and plans, with flexible uptake pathways depending on the institutional mandate of associated partners.

➤ Reference policy documents on the Polish side (AP-driven):

1. Lower Silesian Water Policy (Dolnośląska Polityka Wodna, DPW) developed by IRT.
2. Action Plan for Climate Neutrality in the Lower Silesian Voivodeship (Plan działań w zakresie neutralności klimatycznej) developed by IRT

➤ Interaction with basin-level / high-level water planning documents:

In parallel, the project analyses river basin management and international basin documents for the Oder, but the practical cooperation model is more “alignment and compliance check” than “co-drafting”, because these instruments follow strict update cycles and formal procedures largely outside the project’s control and timeline. This implies that the addendum will primarily target institutions working with these documents (regional/local planning, advisory bodies, municipal implementers), rather than assuming direct authorship or ownership by Wody Polskie or MKOOpZ.

Key dependencies or constraints (for example data gaps, technical problems, legal constraints, timing) that may hinder the Pilot Actions:

Planning cycle and formal update constraints: WFD / Flood Directive-driven instruments follow strict planning cycles and update rules that do not align neatly with the project

timeframe; Wody Polskie and MKOOpz are not project's AP's, and did not declare to work on addendum. Therefore the addendum may be proposed as a voluntary technical reference rather than a formally annexed document.

Stakeholders who will consult and validate addenda, plan for cooperation:

Primary associated partner and key consultation counterpart in Poland is IRT (directly involved in developing DPW and the regional climate neutrality action plan). Cooperation is ongoing to ensure the addendum is tailored to their planning needs and realistic uptake routes.

Additional consultation and validation channels:

- municipalities required to update local adaptation planning,
- advisory and planning service providers,
- national and research bodies reached through project events and stakeholder engagement (examples include IOŚ and relevant ministries as part of the wider consultation landscape).
- Sendzimir Foundation (UPWr's second AP), as an institution with extensive experience in climate change adaptation plays an advisory and supporting role

A work schedule that includes peer to peer collaboration between regions.

PP08 works in a joint tri-border setup with PP07 and PP09, including coordinated cross-border events and a shared addendum workflow supported by regular (bi-weekly) coordination meetings and division of responsibilities.

PP09 Regional Work Plan

Which Pilot Action(s) PP is involved in,

PP09 is involved in three Pilot Actions: PA1 (heat and drought), PA2 (flooding), and PA3 (biodiversity).

What type of addendum or contribution is realistically feasible in PPs context

PP09 will work a) on regional addendum within the pilot area of Liberec region, and b) on tri-border addendum jointly with PP07 (IOER) and PP08 (UPWr), focused on the Neisse/Nysa/Nisa catchment context and on avoiding maladaptation caused by cross-border governance, methodological and data inconsistencies. Most realistic contributions are forms of practical uptake and targeted updates rather than formally binding document creation or changes:

- (1) a revision of the analytical part of the City of Hrádek nad Nisou adaptation strategy focused on climate change impacts
- (2) placing a dashboard link into regional digital infrastructure (DataPortal LK / Geoportal LK), with the main added value in open data or guideline database
- (3) preparing dashboard-based case studies and recommendations coordinated via Euroregion Nisa for PP07/PP08/PP09 stakeholders (building on scientific outputs)
- (4) adding a dashboard link on the official website of the Czech Ministry of the Environment.

Key dependencies or constraints (for example data gaps, technical problems, legal constraints, timing) that may hinder the Pilot Actions

Several constraints may hinder progress. Stakeholders have limited time capacity and often low interest in adopting new tools, while key reference documents are not currently under revision, which reduces windows of opportunity for formal integration. The Czech context already includes multiple existing data portals and platforms, creating potential overlap and reducing perceived added value unless the dashboard provides clear benefits. PP09 also notes an institutional constraint: as a research institute, it has no legal authority to implement changes in official strategic documents. Key risks/bottlenecks include potential changes in political priorities, challenges with official uptake of the addendum/LOI, mismatches between stakeholder expectations and dashboard functionality, possible delays in dashboard launch, and capacity limits (expertise/time) within the team.

Stakeholders who will consult and validate addenda, plan for cooperation

Consultation and validation are expected to involve the institutions linked to the local addendum/LOI and pilot activities, namely the City of Hrádek nad Nisou, the Liberec Region, the Czech Ministry of the Environment, and Euroregion Nisa, alongside the tri-border partner collaboration with PP07 and PP08 for the Neisse river addendum. Cooperation is planned through online webinars (with officials from environment and regional development departments, mayors and deputy mayors invited), complemented by bilateral online/offline meetings during the Pilot Actions and tri-border meetings/events to align and validate outputs across the cross-border territory.

A work schedule that includes peer to peer collaboration between regions.

The work schedule presented combines capacity building with iterative co-creation and validation. It starts with online training webinars in January–February (recordings made available on YouTube), building a shared baseline of understanding and supporting stakeholder readiness. In parallel and following the trainings, PP09 plans bilateral

meetings with key institutions to test needs, refine expected outputs, and support uptake options (e.g., analytical revisions or dashboard linking). Peer-to-peer collaboration is embedded through the preparation of the joint Neisse river addendum with PP07 and PP08, supported by tri-border meetings/events coordinated with Euroregion Nisa to consult stakeholders and validate joint recommendations and case-study outputs.

Triborder pilot region

PP07, PP08 and PP09 will cooperate to create three triborder addenda, organise joint activities and engage stakeholders from all three countries. Details concerning stakeholders and addenda are provided in partner's report.

Key dependencies or constraints (for example data gaps, technical problems, legal constraints, timing) that may hinder the Pilot Actions

Barriers identified during internal brainstorming, workshops and bilateral meetings with stakeholders:

- Cross-border governance differences: divergent administrative responsibilities, declarations, and decision procedures across PL-DE-CZ can lead to inconsistent measures and risk maladaptation (including upstream-downstream conflicts).
- Political and institutional continuity risks: changes in public institutions can cause lack of continuation of predecessor's strategy and approach, disrupt follow-up and reduce the chance of uptake.
- Language barrier and capacity limits: translation burden, uneven data literacy, and limited staff time in local administrations.
- Data constraints: missing, hard-to-find, non-comparable datasets; methodological differences in how indicators are defined and used across borders.
- Risk of "technical overkill": too much technical detail can reduce usability for decision-makers and weaken uptake.

Addendum time plan:

- Feb 2026 Division of responsibilities ✓
- April 2026 Finalize the analysis, literature survey and draft of introduction
- May 2026 Consultation meeting with stakeholders on first results and findings
- May/June 2026 Finalize assessments, collate findings and provide first set of coherent draft manuscript
- August 2026 Provide draft addendum and polished manuscript, provide addendum to respective APs
- Last week of Sept Triborder Event for World River Day - Dissemination event

- October 2026 publication
- Provide final addendum and submit manuscript for